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Disclaimer

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Document information

Additional author(s) and contributing partners

Name	Organisation
Angela Gaitani	Municipality of Nea Smyrni

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Introduction

upPE-T (Upcycling of PE & PET wastes) is a 4-year Research and Innovation Action (RIA) project, which will allow for the first time the upcycling of non-renewable plastics into new biodegradable and recyclable plastics for food and drink packaging application by biotechnological and sustainable routes. upPE-T will also demonstrate its implementation at pilot scale and the validation of the final food and drink products in a real environment. In order to ensure market acceptance of the developed products and sustainability, the project will implement novel standards and basis for future certification schemes applicable to packaging materials from the new bioplastics.

upPE-T Communication & Awareness Plan (CAP) aims at raising awareness to as many relevant actors as possible on the project activities and results. The CAP also aims to fully achieve the expected impact of the upPE-T solution, including the target audiences that should be reached (WHO), the key messages to be conveyed to those audiences (WHAT), the channels and tools to be implemented (HOW), the timing (WHEN) and geographical level (WHERE) of the planned activities.

The plan includes: ▪ Overall communication & awareness strategy and its expected results; ▪ Project visual identity and document templates; ▪ Overarching messages, target groups and tailored key messages; ▪ Identification and segmentation of communication & awareness targets; ▪ Tools and channels needed to implement successful activities; ▪ Description of monitoring tools for the CA activities.

It is worth noting that in order to protect the commercial interests of the participants, the publication of the materials will be selective, except for submission of contractually required reports and information to the Commission. In this case, partners decide which part of the projects' information is to be protected by copyright or trade secrets and which part of the above information is suitable for communicating widely.

The Municipality of Nea Smyrni (MoNS) leads upPE-T Communication & Awareness activity within the project, but all consortium partners will be involved in it.

Communication is a continuous process that needs to be seen as essential for the results of the project, itself.

All the actions will consider EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication (https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm)

The scope and objectives of the CAP

The Communication & Awareness Plan aims at promoting a structured pathway for the project and create connections between European stakeholders with a wide outreach. The present CAP has been developed to support and enhance the project reach regarding the objectives. Not only the best technologies and techniques will be implemented to disseminate project outputs, but constant monitoring and in-depth evaluation will also be carried out to gauge the impact of the suggested actions. Monitoring involves a systematic collection of data and reporting of information from the on-going communication activities. It has to be highlighted that information regarding pre-set key performance indicators (KPI's) will be taken into account. Results will deliver final verdict on the impact and success of the communication process.

More specifically the UpPE-T's Communication & Awareness Plan aims at:

- Raising European citizens awareness about cooperative & innovative projects as an effective way to meet social & environmental challenges
- Increasing environmental awareness as a whole
- Properly communicating the benefits of material & products upcycling and the need for food & drink packaging to be recycled and produced from removable sources
- Facilitating the quick acceptance of upPE-T solution and innovative technologies and products within European industry
- Promoting new sustainable and efficient solutions combining multi-sectorial approach among decision-makers

The CAP is based on:

- A clear definition of objectives
- Overarching messages, target groups and tailored messages
- Visual identity and document templates
- Tools and channels that will be used to implement successful activities

The CAP, within awareness scope, will also include a Roadmap (prepared in task 9.4. **European Citizens Awareness enablers**) to effectively implement the *Awareness Strategy* of the project.

Gender dimension will be widely addressed within upPE-T SSH approach framework, through study, assessment and results implementation. Within Task 7.3. Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and gender aspects addressed through the upPE-T project will also be taken into account in the CAP. Communication and awareness activities will be planned and implemented tailored to individual needs as identified following the analysis of consumers' behaviour, including gender perspective, towards: recycling engagement, food & drink plastics packaging perceptions, etc.

Scope

The objectives of the communication actions are to:

- ✓ Promote the project and its outputs to the largest possible audience, maximizing the expected impacts of upPE-T
- ✓ Deliver tailored communication & awareness actions to specifically targeted audiences;
- ✓ Inform and educate all relative audiences
- ✓ Make new allies and synergies
- ✓ Implement and follow a dedicated stakeholder engagement strategy
- ✓ Ensure that the outputs will be sustained after the end of the project lifetime.
- ✓ Deliver European Citizen Awareness enablers
- ✓ Exchange of results, information and findings with end-users, stakeholders and other relevant parties is envisaged.

The strategic Messaging

Strategic messaging is the core medium to spread the cause and thus must be designed and tailored with each of the stakeholders in order to adapt each audience. It has to be noted that the following messages will be evolved in pertinent messages for all audiences, both specialized and non-specialized, in a way that they can understand actions and results of upPE-T project.

Core Messaging to be distributed to EU public sphere:

- H2020 €7.8 million funding contribution to research and develop an innovative solution for the upcycling PE and PET post-consumer packaging wastes b
- The €7.8 million project 'upPE-T' will champion the upcycling of food and drink packaging PE & PET post-consumer wastes to obtain high value products that will be used in the production of biodegradable & recyclable bioplastics (PHBVs) for food & drink packaging manufacturing.
- The upPE-T project will contribute to upcycling up to 60% of food and drink packaging plastic waste by 2030 and develop a viable roadmap to ensure that 60% of the above packaging will be produced from renewable sources by 2030.
- The 4-year project will increase awareness among EU citizens of products and materials upcycling capacity, bring positive environmental benefits by decreasing 85.6% CO₂ compared to conventional plastics production, contribute to European and international standards and certification schemes
- upPE-T is coordinated by CETEC, Spain and involves a total of 20 European partners from 10 countries including 7SMEs, a Large Enterprise, 5 Universities, 4 RTOs, a Municipality, a Consumers Organisation (UNC), and a Standard Development Organisation (UNE).

Target Audiences

The audience for Communication action is broken down into the following main groups:

Businesses	Academia/ Research Institutes	Government/ authorities	Society
<input type="checkbox"/> Businesses in plastic industry <input type="checkbox"/> Food and agrofood industries <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling system corporations <input type="checkbox"/> Upcycling organisations <input type="checkbox"/> Biotech industries	<input type="checkbox"/> Educational Institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Research Institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Academia experts <input type="checkbox"/> Think tanks	<input type="checkbox"/> Elected officials at EU, national, regional and local level. <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers at EU, national and local levels	<input type="checkbox"/> European Citizens <input type="checkbox"/> Young people <input type="checkbox"/> Communities (local authority forums and groups focusing on environmental issues)

Figure 1: upPE-T communication target audience

The project aims to reach, at least: 100,000 European citizens; 1,500 Industries and 500 Public & Private decision Makers.

The process of identifying the key persons and entities that embody the target and stakeholder groups has already begun, developing a more detailed list to be the target for all communication activities.

TARGET AUDIENCE	TAILORED MESSAGE
General public: • European Citizens • Young public(with adapted messages)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Innovation & cooperation is key to adopt new sustainable models based on circular economy principles; Upcycling is key to reshape current waste recycling approach → Showing social & environmental benefits of upPE-T upcycling process as example of the high impact of cooperation & innovation. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Our production and consumption patterns affect limited resource stocks, generate waste and harm to the environment; Reinventing plastics for the circular economy and addressing their lifecycle is key to address environmental threats → Showing biobased & biodegradable plastics, as PHA is, environmental benefits. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Food and drink packaging must be recycled. Especially, those with short-shell life must be made produced from renewable sources.
General European Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bioplastics as a European solution to decrease dependence on fossil resources and limit the loss of competitiveness against low-wage countries. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic waste is a valuable resource that should be upcycled and re-enter into the value chain, creating profitable businesses for the entire value chain. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Introducing biotechnological processes in the recycling sector will open new business opportunities while helps addressing environmental challenges.
Public & Private EU decision makers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creating an enabling business & regulatory environment is key to market uptake of innovations for resource efficiency & waste management. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Need for legislative in <i>Bio-packaging waste management, bioplastics standardization</i> . Need for consumers awareness pushing towards biopackaging. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> upPE-T will drive Europe towards the adoption of this new green economy model. The potential of materials and products upcycling will make Europe a stronger global actor to boost jobs, growth and investment while implementing sustainable policies towards

Figure 2: upPE-T target audience and tailored message

1 Stakeholders Engagement

Stakeholders Engagement will determine the volume of the project and how wide the community of upPE-T will become. Stakeholders are those who will spread the core messages of the project, influence policy makers and advocates, while educating relative institutions. Thus, the actions that will become the main pillars of stakeholders' engagement strategy will determine the final outcome.

Main actions for stakeholders' engagement include:

- Project Events
- Dialogue Roundtable
- Workshop Events

Stakeholders Mapping:

In the initial phase of the project a mapping of stakeholders will take place in order to identify the potential stakeholders’:

- positivity/negativity
- interest (high or low)
- power or influence (high or low)
- influence per geographic area (local/ national/ international)

This will allow us to classify the stakeholders according to their interest, identify their needs and expectations and create a strategy to manage them.

In addition a stakeholders’ register will be created which will be organized into sections (e.g., groups of columns with specific colors) such as:

- IDENTIFICATION: Stakeholder name, (organization or person), contact email, etc.
- CLASSIFICATION: positive or negative, level of interest, level of power
- EXPECTATIONS: this could be a note field in which to write down briefly what we know/expect from the project

A Stakeholder Engagement Plan (ShEP) will also be developed in order to decide what, how, when, to whom to communicate. This will be dynamic and will assist us in better managing the project resources and build meaningful indicators which are useful for monitoring.

2 General Public Engagement

Strategic messages deriving by the project and awareness activities will be designed, agreed and implemented, in order to educate and influence the European Public Sphere

These actions will become part of a wide calendar and stakeholders will take part in each of them, in a consistent process to increase awareness of products and materials for upcycling -improving consumers’ behaviour and attitude towards drink & food packaging recycling and purchasing.

Actions proposed include:

- European citizens’ awareness Platform and Virtual Reality (VR) based mobile app
- A Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) for European citizens
- Awareness events such as workshops at educational institutions, visits to plastic waste recycling plants,
- European Citizens Awareness Platform
- General fairs/infodays,
- Educational events

In upPE-T project citizen’s awareness campaigns will be implemented with clear information about the complex world of plastics and environmental problems, by making the message feel personal, urgent and local will help citizens to make their own informed choices. A European citizens’ awareness Platform and Virtual Reality (VR) based mobile app will be developed in upPE-T for creating wide awareness among European citizens about plastics upcycling and its benefits.

Education on bio-based products and their properties should start early so that people know more about these topics from a young age. As consumers of the future, their decisions will be crucial for this also young industry. Thus, specific awareness tools will be elaborated in upPE-T to target young population. A Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) for European citizens specially focused on children and youngsters will be developed as part of the project.

3 Creating a roadmap to increase awareness among several groups

A roadmap will be elaborated in order to reach all type of audiences with the correct message, in language and formats tailored to each group needs. The goal is to give these groups the tools to increase their ability to understand environmental problems and further increasing their knowledge & awareness regarding materials and products upcycling, and improve consumer's attitude and behaviour with respect to purchasing and recycling food & drink packaging.

Key message to spread: Upcycling increases quality and lifetimes of materials and products, reduces wastes, creates employment opportunities and encourages sustainable consumer behaviour. upPE-T project vision is the perfect example for showing the benefits of upcycling. Moreover, upPE-T message will spread the need of packaging recycling and the importance of acquire packaging from renewable source to contribute to decarbonise the society.

This roadmap will target:

- **Students and young public.** They are the main pillars of mid-term and long-term society. It is thus essential to give them the tools and knowledge to increase their ability to actively participate within global challenges debates.
- **Public in general.** tailored messages will be specified to identified target groups and needs, with the aim to increase in short term the public's knowledge and ability to understand current faced challenges and

Most of the **people in the bioplastics industry** have a scientific and technical background, which make it more challenging to spread the message through to a non-scientific and non-technical audience. While people with scientific and technological backgrounds are more likely to be convinced with rational arguments, data and facts, the vast majority of people without such kind of background are more likely to be convinced with more emotional arguments, which allow connection with the person.

All actors, from researchers and innovators to institutions and governments will be engaged through inclusive, participatory methodologies in all stages of R&I processes and in all levels of R&I (from agenda setting, to design, implementation, and evaluation) according to RRI principles. All actors participating in upPE-T have been allocated within one or more fields according to their nature and role in the project. Advisory Group members have been also included as they are an essential part of the project processes in engaging societal actors and align the outcomes of the project with social needs and expectations.

Channels

For communication activities, upPE-T project will use a wide range of channels and actions, covering from promotional materials to media relations, using social media campaigns, setting up a website and building a community of interested users around the project (see Figure2).

Besides the ones mentioned, all partners will make use of their channels (website, presence on Social Media and corporate newsletters / publications) to communicate news about upPE-T and reach a broader audience.

Figure 3: upPE-T communication channels

A summary of tools and channels that will be used was outlined in upPE-T application form.

CHANNELS AND TOOLS TO REACH TARGET AUDIENCE	
<p>ONE-WAY COMMUNICATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Website & Social media -All audiences ✓ 2 videos- At the beginning (1 Introducing the project, 1 at the end (main results)- All audiences ✓ 8 Press releases -General public ✓ 2 Radio or TV programs- General public ✓ 3 Infographics: 1 Environment issues & circular economy, 1 materials & products upcycling,1 recycling food & drink packaging-General public ✓ 8 Newsletters- Subscribers & stakeholders from project data base ✓ 2 project leaflets (project beginning, project end)- Industry ✓ Dossiers, posters, brochures (distributed through partners networks and at events)-Industry & Decision Makers ✓ Policy Review-Decision makers 	<p>TWO-WAY COMMUNICATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ European citizens' awareness Platform- General Public ✓ Participation in 10 general fairs/ infodays - Policy makers & Industry ✓ Educational workshops and events-Young public

Figure 4: upPE-T channels

The project will also use the freely accessible tools provided by the European Commission including:

- Horizon Magazine - <http://horizon-magazine.eu/>
- Project stories - <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/newsroom/551/>
- research*eu results magazine - www.cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/magazine_en.html
- research*eu focus - www.cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/research-focus_en.html
- Newsletters - www.ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=publishations&lg=en
- Futuris Magazine - <http://www.euronews.net/sci-tech/futuris/>
- Events on the Commission's Research & Innovation website www.ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=conferences&filter=all
- Events on the CORDIS website www.cordis.europa.eu/news/home_en.html
- Headlines on the Commission's Research & Innovation website www.ec.europa.eu/research/infocentre/all_headlines_en.cfm

4 UpPE-T Project's Visual Identity

The Municipality of Nea Smyrni, as the leader of Communication and Awareness Activity has developed upPE-T's Visual Identity, including the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities and a visual identity standards guidebook, defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to upPE-T including logos, colours, fonts, stationery and some marketing and advertising materials.

Following the project's visual identity manual, a **poster layout** following upPE-T visual image will be produced.

4.1 upPE-T Logo

upPE-T logo aims to represent the different concepts surrounding the project. As pictured below the project's logo - based on a light green and light blue colour palette, with bold fonts - reflects the values and the idea of sustainability and nature elements.

Figure 5: upPE-T logo

4.2 Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual

A visual identity and standards guidebook will be produced and distributed among partners to ensure that project's branding is not compromised and all partners use the elements properly in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand.

Partners have to treat the guidebook as a source of the materials and instructions as a basis for further development of the project's materials. See below some parts of the manual:

Figure 6: Visual Identity analysis

Figure 7: Visual Identity analysis

Figure 8: Visual Identity fonts

Figure 9: Visual Identity logos

4.3 Word and PowerPoint Templates

Communication Leader MoNS has prepared a set of templates, which have been shared with partners. These materials will be used throughout all the project's execution to maintain a coherent and consistent image.

The set of templates includes:

- template for project deliverables
- template for general project documents
- template for project PowerPoint presentations/Word documents

Title of document

Placeholder text for document title, consisting of several lines of dummy text.

Document Title	WPS Stakeholders Meeting Minutes	engagement
Meeting	Microsoft Teams	
Dissemination level	Confidential	
Date and time	01/02/2021 at 12:00 - 13:00 CET	
Author	Angela (Gibart, Nord) WPS lead	

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Figure 10: View of some pages of the project's templates.

5 Website

The project website is intended to serve as communication (and dissemination as well) tool. It will be used as a gateway to diffuse project information as widely as possible.

The MoNS is responsible for designing and implementing the official upPE-T project website, to be launch on M6 (April 2021). The registered URL is www.uppet.eu

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. The website is the anchor for all communication activities related to the project and serve as a central point of entry for all public material, including the project's basic information, all project-related resources/results generated and public deliverables. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active two years after the project's finalisation.

The website platform will follow the corporate visual identity of the project created by MoNS and approved by partners and it will give access to upPE-T social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn). The language used in the website is English. It is essential that the website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smart phones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

5.1 Website structure

MoNS agreed with partners the following Information architecture for upPE-T website:

Figure 11: Structure of upPE-T’s website main menu

Home

The Home page depicts the vision, the main aim and the basic info of the upPE-T project as it’s shown in the following image.

Figure 12: upPE-T website's home page

About us

This section includes information about the consortium and the Advisory Board.

- Consortium

The upPE-T project is composed by 20 partners across Europe. The page includes the logo of each partner and more information about each partner is revealed by clicking on their logo.

Figure 13: upPE-T about us webpage

- Advisory Board

This section of the website will outline the role and responsibilities of the project's Advisory Board.

The Project

- Project overview
- Technology
- Objectives
- Outputs
- Impact
- Results
- Publications (Policy papers, Best practice book, reports)
- Project schedule
- Links to other relevant projects

News

This section is for publishing any news related to the project. i.e: about meetings, first results, publications, etc. News articles will be published regularly by

Communication Leader MoNS with the input of Dissemination leader and all partners in order to generate content to feed the project's social media and increase the traffic to the website. News articles will be categorized in self-explanatory categories to facilitate filtering.

This page will also include an agenda announcing events where upPE-T is attending / participating (conferences, fairs, congresses, workshops, etc.) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile/audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

- Press Releases
- Newsletter
- Events
- Media
- Promotional material

Get involved

- Why join? (button become a stakeholder)
- Stakeholders
- Community engagement
- European Citizens Awareness (link to the Platform)
- Upcoming events and workshops

Contact Us

This section shows the emails for visitors to send comments and questions.

On the other hand, the email info@uppet.eu has been created and is shown at the website as another way of contact. The executive board has access to that email in order to manage all information requests received.

5.2 Layout

The website **menu will be available from all pages**, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they arrived on the site.

The overall design and homepage of the website includes the following elements:

Header

- upPE-T logo to appear in the header
- Navigation menu
- Search button

Footer

- European Union logo to appear in the footer. Under the logo will appear the phrase 'This project has received funding from the European Union's

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953214’.

- Access to Social Media platforms (Twitter and LinkedIn)
- Link to Terms and conditions

5.3 Managing and updating policy

The website will be developed by MoNS with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

The website will be updated by the Communication Leader MoNS together with the inputs sent by all partners every time a new dissemination action is done, a result is achieved, or there is other news worth publishing.

News worthiness will be established at consortium level. The upload policy for public contractual deliverables will be as follows:

1. As soon as the document has been accepted by the Consortium after the internal peer-reviews, an executive summary will be made available.
2. Once the deliverable is also approved by the European Commission, it will be then made formally public in PDF format provided it is at public dissemination level.

5.4 Analytics

The upPE-T website will use Google analytics to monitor all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site’s performance.

Google Search Console will be used to upload the file robots.txt to make easier for Google Robots the indexation.

5.5 Site hosting, installation & maintenance

MoNS is responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase and hosting), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

As the Communication leader, MoNS will be responsible for maintaining the site until the project’s end and until two years after and adding content to the website.

All pages will be optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that upPE-T website is well positioned in the browsers.

5.6 Data protection

MoNS will ensure that upPE-T website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR.

6 Digital print and printed materials

upPE-T project will create communication materials such as an **infographics, two leaflets, a roll-up and eight newsletters**. These materials will serve as the project's business card and will be distributed/communicated as widely as possible, including the general public, conferences, workshops, general fairs, infodays, educational and other events, from the beginning of the project. All these documents will have the online version to be published in the official website and will be distributed among partners digitally for printing.

A pre-packaged set of media usage materials of the project will be developed and distributed through traditional media channels for publicity use. This media kit including a **project fact sheet, a poster and a project brochure** will allow the project to reach large audiences effectively in a short period of time. The project brochure will be produced at first while a version of factsheet is highly recommended.

It is also recommended an updated version of the project brochure to be released, when project outputs are substantial and solid. The project poster will add value as a communication tool with great visual impact to illustrate key project concepts and facts. The project poster will be displayed at the project events and, whenever possible, at exhibition events to which project partners will participate. The project fact sheet, brochure and poster will be uploaded in digital format on the project website and it will be easy to download and share.

Furthermore, to communicate upPE-T objectives and results **two videos** will be produced, **one video** in the middle of the project and **a final project video** based on the project's main outputs and results ready for the closure event. The videos will be uploaded on the project's website and will have a clear reference to EC support via the Horizon 2020 programme.

A promotional video introducing the project, its partnership and activities will be created in order to be disseminated among European countries. The promotional video will be posted onto the project website and relayed through the YouTube and platforms for maximum visibility. The video project is suggested to include facts about upPE-T, the reasoning why the project is crucial for sustainability and environment and some information about the scope.

It is also suggested that video content of events linked with the project such as webinar recordings and event trailers during the project lifetime can be used, edited and posted on website and social media in order to promote awareness. At any circumstances the components and the content of the video will be agreed and validated by partners.

On the other hand, a pack of **upPE-T project images** for partner's free use will be made available through the project's shared drive. Partners will be also able to contribute with non-confidential and free-of-use images to be used for internal and external presentations of project-related materials. **All images shared will have first the approval of the Executive Board and the consortium.**

7 Social media

The social media strategy will add value and will create a dynamic stream of information to the relative audiences, focusing on strengthening the project presence in the European online public sphere. Social media activities will help increase the project impact and relay information as widely as possible in Europe. Considered as powerful interactive media tool, they will serve as a platform to discuss, comment, consult and suggest research and policy topics with different stakeholders at different levels.

MoNS will manage upPE-T's social media accounts and its contents described hereinafter. upPE-T project will use a **Twitter Channel**, [@t_uppe \(Twitter\)](#) and a **LinkedIn account** [upPE-T Project](#).

On the other hand, partners will contribute to spreading the word on their corporate and personal Social Media channels, including accounts in Facebook, Twitter or LinkedIn.

The project coordinator will be in charge of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels.

7.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the top online site for professional, social, and career networking. The site functions as an online directory of individual professionals and organizations, and facilitates the process of professional networking. As of 2021, LinkedIn had more than 740 million members in more than 200 countries.

Figure 14: upPE-T LinkedIn account

MoNS will create a **bimonthly content plan** to be disseminated through LinkedIn. All consortium partners can propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed for this channel and can spread the word through their own channels.

LinkedIn will be used to share news about upPE-T developments; communicate upcoming meetings, workshops, events; share news published in the website to increase traffic to the website; connect with people and groups from the same industry.

7.2 Twitter

Twitter is the 2.0 tool most used by the European Commission to now disseminate the H2020 program, so its creation has full meaning. The account will be managed by MoNS with the support of project partners for the correct management of the account.

upPE-T main objective on Twitter is to reach its raising awareness on the project's aim, as well as promoting the project's results to the specific key stakeholders and the broad audience. Twitter allows to reach directly targeted audiences from validated professional accounts.

Figure 15: upPE-T Twitter account

7.2.1 Account management

MoNS will create a **bimonthly content plan** to be disseminated through Twitter. All consortium partners can propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed for this channel and can spread the word through their own channels.

Comments and answers will be managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

7.2.2 Strategy

When creating and publishing content on the networks about the project, MoNS and the rest of the partners will consider the following recommendations in order to maximize the impact of the messages.

The strategy mixes marketing content, branding and influence actions to maximise upPE-T's project impact and encourage market uptake, to secure a critical mass of early adopters among consumers.

7.2.2.1 Content strategy includes:

- Sponsor the organization of meetings, reviews, and achievement of milestones, including text and photos if possible.
- Content curation: sharing news about upPE-T developments, circular economy, European policies, etc.
- Give visibility to the videos made for the project (to make the project more accessible/understandable)
- Sharing news and blog posts published in the website to increase traffic to the website.
- Promote through social media the project to increase the number of followers.
- To increase the reach of the tweets, it is proposed the frequent use of the following hashtags, usual in other areas within the scope of the project:
#upPE-T H2020 #plastic #food packaging #circular economy
#ResearchImpactEu #Horizon2020 #H2020 #EUcircular economy
- Mention project partners when publishing news about them to promote likes and retweets from partners.

7.2.2.2 Branding strategy includes:

- Twitter covering in fairs where upPE-T is presented using the official hashtag of the event
- upPE-T's Twitter official account will be referenced in the partner's corporate accounts for a broader reach of the project.

7.2.2.3 Influencers' strategy:

- Regularly mention @EU_H2020, @UPPET H2020, @H2020 PROJECT, @UPPET, @H2020 PROJECT in order to get a bigger impact when project news or information about results is published.
- Identify and mention influencers/stakeholders in the field of circular economy, plastic and food packaging
- Identification of stakeholder's accounts to promote follow-back and to increase the number of upPE-T followers.
- Media will be mentioned if they are publishing information about the project.

7.2.2.4 Following and followers

Our reputation on Twitter depends on the number of users we follow. There must be a balanced number between our followers and the users we follow. Otherwise, it is considered that the tool is being misused, since the objective is to share knowledge bidirectionally.

Therefore, upPE-T will follow people and organizations related to the project's topic. At the first stage of the project, upPE-T Twitter account will follow all project partners, as well of institutions, centres and professionals in the field of the project, which will be identified during the first months of the project. The media, as well as Twitter profiles of reference bloggers, covering the project topic will also be followed.

We will avoid followers with an offensive avatar (for example, pornographic, racist) or spammers, which we will block.

7.2.2.5 First battery of tweets

During the first months of the project, is proposed a content strategy on more generic tweets about the project. As the project is being executed, content on specific results, news and posts and specific advances in each of the project's use-cases will be disseminated through Twitter.

7.2.2.6 Analytics

A profile in Twitter Analytics will be activated in order measure Twitter's KPIs and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

7.2.3 YouTube

The project will use the method of storytelling for putting objectives and results of the upPE-T research project closer to the general public. Interviews of project partners about their role in the project will be recorded and produced in a video and will then be published in a YouTube channel as well on the project's website and Social Media Accounts. A content driven marketing of the project will follow when all partners have been interviewed.

Youtube account will also serve as a content repository of all audio-visual content that will be produced during the project.

7.2.4 Partners' channels

Each partner will transmit upPE-T news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook), including press releases, notices about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.uppet.eu or in upPE-T's twitter account.

upPE-T partners impact in social media channels will reach **1000 users on Twitter and** more than **1000 on LinkedIn** followers.

The corporate accounts to be used are:

Partners Name	Link to Facebook page	Link to Twitter account
CETEC. Centro Tecnológico del Calzado y del Plástico. Región de Murcia	https://www.facebook.com/CETEC-Centro-Tecnol%C3%B3gico-del-Calzado-y-del-Pl%C3%A1stico-Regi%C3%B3n-de-Murcia-1597624903898517/	https://twitter.com/ceteccentro?lang=el
ENZYMICALS AG		
Eco Plastics	https://www.facebook.com/EcoPlasticsSerbia	
CTCR. Centro Tecnológico del Calzado de La Rioja	https://www.facebook.com/CTCRioja/#!/pages/CTCR-Centro-Tecnol%C3%B3gico-del-Calzado-de-La-Rioja/295467837169157?sk=wall	https://twitter.com/CTCRioja
BOKU - Universität für Bodenkultur Wien	https://www.facebook.com/bokuvienna/	https://twitter.com/bokuvienna
TAMK - Tampere University of Applied Sciences	https://www.facebook.com/tampereenamk/	https://twitter.com/tamk_uas?lang=el
LAPPEENRANTA-LAHTI UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY	https://www.facebook.com/unilut/?ref=page_internal	https://twitter.com/unilut?lang=el
Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.	https://www.facebook.com/Tecnoalimenti-SCpA-123129514413829/?ref=page_internal	
Institut za razvoj i inovacije	https://www.facebook.com/iri.institut/	https://twitter.com/iri_institut
DIGIOTOUCH	https://www.facebook.com/Digiotouch-OU-300654287289676/	https://twitter.com/digiotouch
UNIONE NAZIONALE CONSUMATORI	https://www.facebook.com/consumatoriumbria/	https://twitter.com/UmbriaUnione
ΔΗΜΟΣ ΝΕΑΣ ΣΜΥΡΝΗΣ	https://www.facebook.com/MunicipalityOfNeaSmirni/	
DURUKAN CONFECTIONERY INC	https://www.facebook.com/DurukanSekelme/	https://twitter.com/ikdurukancomtr2
ASOCIACIÓN ESPANASOCIACIÓN ESPAÑOLA DE NORMALIZACIÓN		https://twitter.com/NormasUNE
CETEC BIOTECHNOLOGY	https://www.facebook.com/CETEC-Centro-Tecnol%C3%B3gico-del-Calzado-y-del-Pl%C3%A1stico-Regi%C3%B3n-de-Murcia-1597624903898517/	https://twitter.com/ceteccentro?lang=el
UNIVERSIDAD DE ALICANTE	https://www.facebook.com/campusUA/	https://twitter.com/UA_Universidad
BIO-MI	https://www.facebook.com/biomisolutions/	https://twitter.com/mi_sustainable
VILLANI SALUMI S.P.A	https://www.facebook.com/VillaniSalumi	https://twitter.com/villanisalumi?lang=el
MOSES PRODUCTOS, S.L.	https://www.facebook.com/MosesProducts/	https://twitter.com/MosesProductos
UNIVERSITÄT GREIFSWALD	https://www.facebook.com/Uni.Greifswald.de/timeline/	https://twitter.com/uni_greifswald

8 Media relations

Press releases will be **written and sent at regular intervals throughout the project** (two press releases per year) focusing on the release of research results, tools and project materials, meetings, attendance to specialised events, conferences, etc. and connected with newsworthy initiatives when possible.

All press releases will be distributed among partners in English, who, after providing feedback, will be able to adapt them in their corporate language and make them circulate throughout their communication channels and sent to their media database.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented for a specific stakeholder group can be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator. Also partners can consider interview-offerings and a press conference at the end of the project to show the main project results to media.

In the framework of the project, a database with the contact details of partners' communication officers will be created, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press releases and increase impact.

On the other hand, a database with specialized media covering circular economy and plastic packaging matters will be created, primarily with outlets located in the partner's countries. Communication Leader MoNS will contact key specialized media and include them in their media database.

9 Newsletters

Project newsletters, released on a quarterly basis, will enable the project to update and inform European community with latest project activities and results. If implemented it is of high importance that Partners provide content for the newsletters and invite additional contacts to subscribe to the newsletter.

Community building and email marketing

Communication Leader MoNS will create a community of people, i.e. stakeholders interested in upPE-T results through posting the **online 'get involved' form for its purpose on the project's website and Social Media.**

All members of the upPE-T group will **receive periodic information** on the project and results to be downloaded. Email marketing campaigns / newsletters will be sent out 1 time during the project's first year (M12), 2 on the 2nd year (M18, M24) and 2 times on the 3rd year (M30, M36), and two in the last year (M42, M48) will be devoted on gaining newsletter subscribers.

Additionally, information about upPE-T project will be included to partners' newsletters or corporate publications.

Communication KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of upPET Key performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the communication activities. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target by the end of the project
Media	Number of press releases	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	>6
	Number of articles, sector press with project acknowledgements	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	>50
Website	Number of web visits	Analytics	>20.000
	Number pages viewed		>10.000
	Number page/session		>1.0
	Number users		>1000
	Avg. session time		>1.0 min
	Number downloads model		>100
Social Media (Twitter)	Number Followers	Twitter Analytics	>1000
	Number Tweets		>50
	Twitter Impressions		>9000
	Number mentions		>20
Social media (Mentions in partners accounts)	Number of posts	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	>20
	Number of likes		>50
	Number of shares/retweets		>10

Table 1: Communication KPIs

